

Observations and Model Simulations of Phase Heterogeneity in Arctic Clouds

Key Points:

- The observed mixed-phase cloud is very heterogeneous and dominated by small pockets of liquid, ice or both
- Model simulations also favor the smallest pockets but predict mean pocket lengths of 10 km, five times larger than observed
- Simulation results indicate that the distribution of phase in mixed-phase clouds could depend on the ice formation pathway

Correspondence to:

S. L.-S. Dammann,
sldamman@uio.no

Citation:

Dammann, S. L.-S., Schäfer, B., David, R. O., & Storelvmo, T. (2025). Observations and model simulations of phase heterogeneity in Arctic clouds. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 130, e2024JD042714. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024JD042714>

Received 19 OCT 2024

Accepted 11 JUN 2025

Stian Leer-Salvesen Dammann¹

¹Department of Geosciences, Section for Meteorology and Oceanography, University of Oslo, Oslo, Norway, ²Business School, Nord University, Bodø, Norway

Abstract Mixed-phase clouds (MPCs) play a key role in Earth's radiation budget particularly in the Arctic where they are ubiquitous year-round. An important characteristic of MPCs is how the cloud phases are mixed, which affects interactions between ice and liquid. Observations show that phase tends to be nonuniform with ice and liquid forming spatially separated single-phased “pockets” not accounted for in climate models. These pockets may vary in size from the micron-scale to several hundred kilometers making them notoriously difficult to study, and the factors influencing cloud-phase heterogeneity remain uncertain. We quantify size distributions of phase pockets in an observed and modeled Arctic MPC occurring 12 November 2019 in Ny-Ålesund, Svalbard. The case is simulated with the Weather Research and Forecasting model constrained with representative aerosol concentrations following measurements from the Ny-Ålesund Aerosol Cloud Experiment. We find that phase pockets exhibit broad size distributions with the smallest pockets occurring most frequently. Observations reveal mean pocket lengths of 2 km, whereas the simulated pockets are about 5 times longer on average. Simulated pocket size distributions are highly sensitive to prescribed aerosols. Moreover, we observe a pronounced increase of 6.5 km in the mean length of mixed-phase pockets when secondary ice production is enhanced in simulations. These results shed light on the link between cloud microphysics and the in-cloud distribution of phase and provide a potential framework for representation of sub-grid scale phase variability in climate models.

Plain Language Summary Mixed-phase clouds contain both liquid water and ice. These are very common and play an important role for Earth's climate. Liquid and ice in these clouds are often separated making them last longer and precipitate less than they would if ice and liquid could interact freely. The separation of liquid and ice is very hard to capture with models because it may occur on scales much smaller than models can resolve. Here, we look at a case study from Ny-Ålesund, Svalbard where we use both direct measurements, remote sensing, and high resolution model simulations to quantify this separation. We find that liquid and ice often come in “pockets” that can be anywhere from several tens of kilometers long down to a few hundred meters and that the smallest pockets are the most common. By comparing several different model simulations, we show that the size of these pockets is connected to the various ways that ice can form in a cloud. These findings contribute to our understanding of how small-scale processes are linked to large-scale properties of the cloud and provide a framework for how phase separation can be studied and eventually represented in climate models in future studies.

1. Introduction

Mixed-phase clouds (MPCs) present a complex system of water in all three phases as solid, liquid, and gas. They are observed across all latitudes and seasons (Shupe et al., 2008) owing partly to the broad range of temperatures, between -38 and 0°C , at which they can form and exist. Their high prevalence means that they provide a substantial contribution to the radiation budget and hydrological cycle (e.g., Matus & L'Ecuyer, 2017; Mülmenstädt et al., 2015).

Initial ice formation in MPCs typically require the presence of ice-nucleating particles (INPs) to facilitate the freezing of supercooled liquid droplets referred to as primary ice production (Kanji et al., 2017). As such, atmospheric INPs play a critical role in determining the microphysical and dynamic processes of MPCs and thereby exert a major influence on macroscale cloud characteristics, such as lifetime, extent, and radiative properties (Burrows et al., 2022). However, observed ice concentrations in MPCs are often much higher than the measured concentrations of atmospheric INPs (e.g., Auer et al., 1969; Hobbs & Rangno, 1990, 1998; Koenig, 1963; Wieder,

© 2025. The Author(s).

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Ihn, et al., 2022). This discrepancy is typically attributed to secondary ice production (SIP), a term describing various processes through which pre-existing ice crystals can form more ice (Ladino et al., 2017). Several SIP mechanisms have been studied over the past decades (e.g., Hallett & Mossop, 1974; Lauber et al., 2018; Phillips et al., 2018; Vardiman, 1978), but despite the large proposed importance of SIP mechanisms for the MPC system, their physical basis still remains poorly understood (Field et al., 2017; Korolev & Leisner, 2020).

Adding to the complexity of the MPC system, MPCs are thermodynamically unstable due to the lower saturation vapor pressure over ice than liquid. Thus, ice crystals may grow at the expense of the supercooled liquid droplets when the phases co-exist in what is referred to as the Wegener-Bergeron-Findeisen (WBF) process (Bergeron, 1928; Findeisen, 1938; Wegener, 1911). The WBF process has significant impacts on several properties of MPCs, such as lifetime, precipitation rates, and composition (Mülmenstädt et al., 2015). However, the WBF process acts only on the microphysical level and is thus dependent on the relative spatial distribution of supercooled liquid droplets and ice particles within the cloud. Any spatial separation of the phases will inhibit the efficiency of the WBF process, implying that the microphysical spatial structure is important for accurate representations of MPCs in numerical weather prediction (NWP) models as well as earth system models (ESMs).

Currently, even though the treatment of cloud microphysics in ESMs has become more sophisticated, many still base their partitioning of ice and supercooled liquid on temperature only. Furthermore, the fact that the temperature of equal abundance differs between models by up to 40°C contributes substantially to the uncertainties in high-latitude cloud feedbacks (McCoy et al., 2015) and highlights the need for further progress. For models that do not employ simple temperature-dependent phase functions, parametrizations of the WBF process typically assume that the phases are uniformly distributed within cloudy grid cells (Storelvmo et al., 2008). Observations suggest that such phase distributions are rare in nature (Korolev et al., 2003, 2017) and that the phases may be separated at scales much smaller than the typical grid resolution used in atmospheric models (D'Alessandro et al., 2021; Korolev & Milbrandt, 2022; Maciel et al., 2024; Sokol & Storelvmo, 2024). As a consequence, both reanalysis products, NWP models, and ESMs have been shown to frequently underestimate the amount of supercooled liquid water in mixed-phase clouds due to an overactive WBF (Cesana et al., 2015; Komurcu et al., 2014; McIlhattan et al., 2017) in turn causing large errors in annual mean downwelling shortwave radiation in both the Arctic and Southern Ocean (Bodas-Salcedo et al., 2016; Naud et al., 2014; Vergara-Temprado et al., 2018).

Recent studies have attempted to characterize the distribution of phase within MPCs. D'Alessandro et al. (2021) devised a method to quantify the degree of heterogeneity from airborne in situ measurements of cloud phase by comparing the number of cloud segments with identical neighboring phases to the total number of phase observations. When applied to cloud probe observations of Southern Ocean MPCs, they associated greater heterogeneity with broader distributions of updraft velocities within the cloud. Similarly, Korolev and Milbrandt (2022) used cloud probe observations from the Arctic to reveal that segments of continuous ice, liquid, and mixed-phase may occur on a cascade of scales ranging from 100 m to 100 km, and that the frequency distribution of segment lengths follows a simple power law dependency. Turbulence was identified as a key factor influencing cloud phase distribution in a study by Yang et al. (2024) where in situ observations were combined with large eddy simulations (LES) of a case study in Northeast China. This study revealed distinct height dependencies of the phase distribution from cloud base to cloud top and showed that a faster glaciation process gives smaller regions of mixed-phase in the LES model. Despite these recent efforts, there are still many unanswered questions related to how cloud phase is distributed in mixed-phase clouds particularly regarding the role of cloud microphysics and ice formation processes (Korolev et al., 2017). A better understanding of the underlying factors that influence and drive mixed-phase processes is crucial to improve representations of middle- and high-latitude clouds in models and to ultimately reduce uncertainties in feedbacks related to clouds and cloud phase in climate projections.

In this study, we use in situ observations and remote sensing to assess how a cloud-resolving model simulates the phase heterogeneity in a case study of an Arctic MPC field. Furthermore, we apply different parameterizations of ice nucleation and secondary ice production processes informed by observations following the Ny-Ålesund Cloud Experiment (NASCENT; Pasquier, David, et al., 2022) campaign to evaluate their role in determining the spatial phase heterogeneity of MPCs. An overview of the case study, relevant data, and the model setup is provided in Section 2, whereas the analysis methods are described Section 3. The results are presented in Section 4, and the

Figure 1. Overview of the model domains (a) and the vertical levels (b) used for the simulations and the measurement sites at Ny-Ålesund (c). The horizontal resolution of the model domains are 15, 5, and 1 km for *d01*, *d02*, and *d03*, respectively. In this study, we use in situ measurements from HoloBalloon and INP measurements from the Swiss Site as well as Cloudnet remote sensing data from the AWIPEV Site. Figure adapted from Pasquier, David, et al. (2022), © American Meteorological Society. Used with permission.

interpretations of them and their implications are provided in Section 5. Lastly, the key findings of this study are summarized in Section 6.

2. Data and Methods

The observational data used in this study were collected during the NASCENT field campaign conducted between September 2019 and August 2020 in Svalbard, Norway (Pasquier, David, et al., 2022). NASCENT was based in Ny-Ålesund on the West coast of Svalbard with five separate measurement sites performing atmospheric measurements regarding aerosols, clouds, radiation, and meteorological properties (Figure 1c).

We focus on a case study from 12 November 2019, when a persistent mixed-phase cloud field was observed. Although the conditions on this day may not fully represent the broader Arctic, they offer valuable insights into

cloud-phase heterogeneity and its controlling processes. Observational evidence was found for a significant contribution of secondary ice to the total cloud ice content on this day (Pasquier, Henneberger, Ramelli, Lauber, et al., 2022). The meteorological conditions were shaped by a warm front that passed over Ny-Ålesund on 11 November. As the front passed and left Ny-Ålesund in the warm sector behind it, a pronounced air temperature increase was seen at the surface with surface air temperatures rising from below -10°C on 10 November to relatively stable temperatures varying between -3 and 0°C on 12 November. 12 November saw many short but intense snow showers with a total of about 2.4 mm of liquid water equivalent precipitation (Pasquier, Henneberger, Ramelli, Lauber, et al., 2022). The observed cloud top height over Ny-Ålesund ranged from about 1300 to 2000 m a.s.l., increasing throughout the day, with cloud top temperatures consequently decreasing from around -11 to -14°C . The cloud base varied between 200 and 600 m a.s.l.

The measurements from the campaign relevant to this study are presented below.

2.1. HoloBalloon

HoloBalloon (Ramelli et al., 2020) is a tethered balloon system designed to carry the HOLOGraphic Imager for Microscopic Objects 3B (HOLIMO3B). HOLIMO3B has a sample volume of approximately 18.6 cm^3 and uses digital in-line holography to size and count hydrometeors with diameters larger than $6\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ within this volume. All hydrometeors with diameters smaller than $25\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ are characterized as liquid droplets, whereas larger hydrometeors are classified as either liquid or ice based on their shape using a convolutional neural network (Touloupas et al., 2020). The mass of cloud liquid water is subsequently calculated based on the resulting droplet size distribution assuming spherical droplets. Similarly, ice mass is estimated following the size-dependent density relationship from Cotton et al. (2013). Three separate flights were performed with HoloBalloon on 12 November 2019, reaching altitudes up to about 850 m a.s.l., with HOLIMO3B operating at a frame rate of 6 holograms per second. Upon post-processing, individual holograms were merged into clusters of 180 to increase the hydrometeor counts yielding a final temporal resolution of 30 s.

2.2. Ice-Nucleating Particle (INP) Measurements

Air samples during the NASCENT campaign were taken from the Swiss site (see Figure 1c) with a high flow-rate liquid-impinger (Coriolis- μ , Bertin Instruments, France). The Coriolis- μ collects aerosols larger than $0.5\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ by rotating the air within a sterilized plastic cone partially filled with distilled water with a collection efficiency of 50%, 80%, and 94% for 0.5, 2, and $5\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ particles, respectively (Wieder, Mignani, et al., 2022). For each measurement, the Coriolis- μ was active for 1 hour with a flow-rate of 300 L min^{-1} sampling a total air volume of 18 m^3 . The resulting solutions were each transferred to 96-well PCR trays and analyzed with the Droplet Ice Nuclei Counter Zürich (DRINCZ; David et al., 2019). DRINCZ allows the PCR trays to be partially submerged into a temperature-controlled ethanol bath, which is cooled at a constant rate of 1 K min^{-1} . The freezing temperature of each individual well is recorded yielding the frozen fraction of the sample as a function of temperature. The frozen fraction is subsequently used to compute the estimated INP concentrations per temperature interval following Vali (1971). The measured INP concentrations were fitted to an exponential function yielding the temperature dependent relationship given by Equation 1 (Pasquier, David, et al., 2022).

$$n_{\text{INP}}(T)[\text{m}^3] = 1000 * \exp(-0.4146 * (T[\text{K}] - 273.15) - 12.4059) \quad (1)$$

Equation 1 was used to replace the default temperature dependency of the immersion mode INP parameterization in the model (see Section 2.4).

2.3. Cloudnet

The Cloudnet project (Illingworth et al., 2007) provides ground-based observations of clouds from several locations around the world, including Ny-Ålesund (Swiss site, Figure 1), by combining a cloud radar with a microwave radiometer and a ceilometer. The target classification product (Hogan & O'Connor, 2004; Illingworth et al., 2007) of Cloudnet makes use of the synergy of the instruments combined with temperature profiles from either atmospheric soundings or short-range weather forecasts to allow for the distinction of cloud phase, as the radar and ceilometer backscatter is sensitive to particles of different sizes. The classification algorithm essentially performs a set of tests on each observed target and attributes a simple yes/no flag to each. The classification

algorithm outputs a number of categories based on the various potential combinations of activated flags. Liquid is returned if the liquid droplet flag is the only one activated usually determined by a strong echo in the ceilometer backscatter. When the flag for “falling target” is active in addition to a registered wet bulb temperature below freezing, the output category is set as ice. The combination of detected droplets, subzero wet bulb temperature, and falling target is indicative of ice and droplets in co-existence interpreted here as mixed-phase. The classification product comes with a native temporal resolution of 30 s (Ebell et al., 2022).

2.4. Cloud-Resolving Model Simulations

The case study was simulated by Schäfer et al. (2024) using the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF; Skamarock et al., 2019) model version 4.0.1. A detailed description of the simulations is provided by Schäfer et al. (2024), but a brief summary of the information most relevant to this study is presented here.

WRF was initialized with input from the European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) 5th generation reanalysis (ERA5) product (Hersbach et al., 2023). Each simulation started on November 11 at noon, allowing 12 hr of spin-up before the start of the case study at midnight on November 12. Boundary layer processes were treated by the Yonsei University scheme (Hong et al., 2006), and longwave and shortwave radiation was parameterized with the CAM scheme (Collins et al., 2004). Each experiment was simulated on three nested domains, $d01$, $d02$, and $d03$, shown in Figure 1a with the primary focus being on the innermost domain $d03$. The domains have horizontal resolutions of 15 ($d01$), 5 ($d02$), and 1 km ($d03$) and use time steps of 30, 10, and 2 s, respectively. All three domains have the same vertical resolution with 172 layers extending up to a height of 17 km, of which approximately half are located in the lower 2500 m where the clouds of interest are located. For the analysis in this study, we only look at the model column from the inner domain $d03$ that approximately coincides with the measurement site of HoloBalloon in Ny-Ålesund.

Cloud microphysics were simulated with the double-moment bulk microphysics parameterization scheme following Morrison et al. (2005) and adapted by Morrison and Grabowski (2008) henceforth referred to as the “Morrison scheme.” The Morrison scheme includes prognostic equations for both mass and number concentrations of cloud ice as well as the precipitating hydrometeor species rain, snow, and graupel. Mixing ratios for cloud droplets are also simulated, but the cloud droplet number concentration (CDNC) is prescribed and set to 250 cm^{-3} in the default version. INP concentrations (INPC) are also prescribed with deposition nucleation following Cooper (1986), immersion freezing following Bigg (1953), and contact nucleation from Meyers et al. (1992).

When compared to in situ aerosol measurements from the campaign, the INPC was found to exceed observations by several orders of magnitude. In-cloud measurements performed with HoloBalloon also indicated that the default value for CDNC was too high for this particular case study. In the simulation henceforth referred to as “Adapted,” INPC and CDNC are thus lowered to match observations. Additionally, the effect of secondary ice production (SIP) is evaluated by including an additional simulation, referred to as “Adapted + SIP,” where several measures are taken to increase the occurrence of SIP. First, the occurrence of the rime splintering (RS) process, being the only SIP pathway parameterized in the default Morrison scheme, is increased achieved by lowering the mixing ratio thresholds of cloud ice and liquid determining its onset as recommended by several previous modeling studies (Atlas et al., 2022; Sinclair et al., 2016; Young et al., 2019). Second, the impact of RS is also enhanced by increasing the number of splinters produced per event (Schäfer et al., 2024). Finally, parameterizations of additional SIP pathways are included in the form of ice crystal breakup (BR) and droplet shattering (DS) following Sotiropoulou et al. (2021) and Georgakaki et al. (2022). The differences between the experiments are summarized in Table 1.

3. Quantifying Cloud Phase Heterogeneity

Cloud phase in the HoloBalloon measurements and the model simulations is determined based on the ice water fraction (IWF) given by the ratio of cloud ice mass (m_{ice}) to total condensed cloud water mass ($m_{liquid} + m_{ice}$) (Equation 2).

$$IWF = \frac{m_{ice}}{m_{ice} + m_{liquid}} \quad (2)$$

Table 1
Summary of the Key Differences Between the WRF Experiments

	Default	Adapted	Adapted + SIP
INPC	Unchanged	Modified	Modified
CDNC	250 cm ⁻³	9 cm ⁻³	9 cm ⁻³
RS	Unchanged	Unchanged	Enhanced
BR	No	No	Yes
DS	No	No	Yes

Note. INPC = Ice nucleating particle concentration, CDNC = cloud droplet number concentration, RS = rime splintering (RS), BR = mechanical breakup, DS = droplet shattering.

Following Korolev et al. (2003) we use an IWF threshold $IWF_T = 0.1$, such that $IWF > 0.9$ is classified as ice phase, $IWF < 0.1$ as liquid phase, and anywhere in between as mixed-phase. Sensitivity to different choices of IWF_T was tested and can be found in the supplement (Appendix C).

We distinguish between the terms “well-mixed” and “homogeneous.” With a well-mixed cloud, we mean a cloud that often consists of liquid and ice in comparable amounts at the smallest resolved scales also referred to in literature as “genuine” or “true” mixed-phase (e.g., Korolev et al., 2017). These cloud volumes are where the WBF process can be the most active as liquid and ice exist in close proximity to each other. This is an important distinction from a homogeneous cloud by which we mean a cloud that exhibits long, consistent segments where few or no phase transitions occur. For a cloud of equal amounts liquid and ice on average, we can have very different scenarios

in terms of homogeneity and degree of mixing as illustrated in Figure 2 where each come with important implications for various cloud properties and radiative effects. Panel A shows a mixed-phase cloud scenario similar to what would be assumed in a typical ES, with the cloud being perfectly homogeneous in addition to perfectly mixed, giving a large potential for a very active WBF process limited only by the ambient supersaturation. This stands in contrast to the case in panel b where the WBF process is limited to the small interface between ice and liquid due to the spatial separation of the phases despite the cloud being relatively homogeneous in terms of having few phase transitions. This highlights the importance of characterizing the degree of both heterogeneity and mixing simultaneously in intermediate cases, such as shown in panel c, in order to be able to represent the microphysical processes of mixed-phase clouds accurately.

In this study, we apply a similar method as introduced by D’Alessandro et al. (2021) to quantify the phase heterogeneity. A segment with consecutive time steps of single-phase is referred to as a phase pocket as illustrated in Figure 3. The length of each pocket L_p is estimated following Equation 3 based on the number of consecutive time steps n of the given phase, the temporal resolution r_T , and the approximate horizontal wind speed of $u_H = 10$ m/s with which the cloud is advected through the measurement location.

$$L_p = nr_T u_H \tag{3}$$

Here, we subsample the data from HoloBalloon and Cloudnet by selecting only every other time step in order to match the 1 min resolution of the model output. The sensitivity of the results to the subsampling was tested and found to be small (see Figure D1 in Appendix D). Given the resulting temporal resolution of 1 min, the minimum pocket detection length is 0.6 km as calculated by Equation 3. The three HoloBalloon flights were performed between 10:00 and 17:00 on 12 November 2019. For comparability, we include only Cloudnet and model data from the same 7 hr period in our analysis. HoloBalloon was measuring in the cloud interior at varying altitudes between approximately 500 and 700 m a.s.l. To cover similar parts of the cloud for the interior comparison, we select all vertical levels in this altitude range in both the model (9 levels in total) and Cloudnet data (30 levels) and compute the pocket lengths for each level individually. The resulting statistics are visualized using cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) for the pocket lengths of each phase separately and when all phases are considered. We use the mean pocket length of any phase as our principal measure of the degree of heterogeneity where smaller pocket lengths correspond to greater heterogeneity.

Figure 2. Schematic illustrating a perfectly homogeneous and perfectly mixed cloud (a), a homogeneous but perfectly unmixed cloud (b), and a perfectly heterogeneous and intermediately mixed cloud (c).

Figure 3. Schematic of the heterogeneity quantification method applied in this paper adapted from D’Alessandro et al. (2021). Each box represents a cloud volume located at the cloud transect at a given time. Blue boxes indicate liquid phase (less than 10% ice), gray corresponds to ice phase (more than 90% ice), and green is mixed-phase.

4. Results

Before we apply the phase classification, we present a brief overview of the observed and modeled cloud properties from the case study. Figure 4 shows the reflectivity measured by the Cloudnet radar (panel a) and how the simulated total water content (TWC) of the three experiments compares with the in situ observations from HoloBalloon (panels b–d). Several intensive snow showers were observed throughout the day evident from the distinct fallstreaks seen in the radar reflectivity (Figure 4a). Observed fallstreaks coincide approximately with periods of elevated TWC in the simulated clouds. Before noon, the simulated cloud tops differ by about 200 m from the maximum altitude of observed reflectance but both predict a distinct cloud-top rise through the day reaching similar altitudes around 15:00. The temperature variations between the simulations are small (see Figure B1), indicating that any cloud microphysical differences between the experiments are due to changes in the

Figure 4. Overview of the observed and modeled cloud properties from the case study. Panel (a) shows the Cloudnet radar and HoloBalloon flight altitude. Panels (b–d) show the modeled total water content (TWC) from *Default* (b), *Adapted* (c) and *Adapted + SIP* (d) experiments compared with the in situ measurements of TWC from HoloBalloon (colored circles along flight path). Dashed lines in panels (a–d) represent the altitudes from which Cloudnet and modeled cloud data are considered for the further analysis and comparison with HoloBalloon. Panels (e–h) show the phase classification from Cloudnet (e), *Default* (f), *Adapted* (g) and *Adapted + SIP* (h) for the same altitude range with the HoloBalloon phase classification superimposed (colored dots).

Figure 5. Occurrence of liquid (blue), mixed (green), and ice-phase (gray) in the cloud interior over Ny-Ålesund as observed by HoloBalloon and Cloudnet and simulated by the WRF experiments *Default*, *Adapted*, and *Adapted + SIP*. Phase occurrence is expressed as percentage of the total number of cloudy time steps.

model microphysics rather than accompanying cloud structural differences or macroscopic properties. HoloBalloon was measuring near the simulated cloud base during all three flights, which coincides with the base of the liquid layer as detected by Cloudnet (not shown).

Panels e–h in Figure 4 show the phase classification output for the altitude range considered in the subsequent results. For both HoloBalloon and the model simulations, the phase classification is derived by applying phase thresholds to the mass-based IWF as described in Section 3. For Cloudnet, the target classification algorithm of Hogan and O’Connor (2004) is used (see Section 2.3). Although Cloudnet does not reproduce the pure liquid classification observed by HoloBalloon, it indicates a high frequency of phase transitions supported by the in situ observations. The phase classification in the model simulations differ significantly between the experiments depending on the microphysics parameterization employed. Both *Default* and *Adapted + SIP* effectively capture the temporal phase structure of the cloud observed during the first two HoloBalloon flights. *Adapted + SIP* is also accurately reproducing the cloud as compared to HoloBalloon during the third flight, whereas *Default* predicts a

Figure 6. Cumulative distribution functions of the pocket lengths measured in kilometers of liquid (a), mixed-phase (b), ice (c), and any phase (Total Cloud; panel d). Dashed lines refer to the median pocket length as given by the intersection with the 0.5 line in the CDF. Minimum detection size is determined by the temporal resolution and the wind speed and is in this case approximately 0.6 km. Note that no liquid was observed by Cloudnet, and consequently no distribution is shown for liquid pockets in Cloudnet.

Figure 7. (a) Mean pocket length in kilometers of each phase (colored dots) and all cloud (bars) in the cloud interior and (b) total number of pockets belonging to each phase. Note that pockets are counted over a different number of cloud layers between Cloudnet (30), model simulations (9) and HoloBalloon (1), and that absolute pocket numbers are therefore not directly comparable between the sources.

much higher degree of glaciation. The intermediate experiment, *Adapted*, struggles with insufficient ice and mixed-phase during the entire simulation period due to the loss of INPs.

The overall phase partitioning in the cloud interior shown in Figure 5 reveals that both liquid, ice, and mixed-phase were observed by the in situ measurements from HoloBalloon and that the cloud was not dominated by any single phase. Cloudnet, on the other hand, shows a cloud mostly dominated by the ice phase with only 25.6% occurrence of mixed-phase and no liquid. This large discrepancy is likely due to difficulties with detecting liquid in Cloudnet (Griesche et al., 2020). All WRF simulations show a much higher liquid occurrence in the interior compared to observations. The *Default* experiment achieves comparable ice occurrence as HoloBalloon but with mixed-phase being substantially underrepresented. When aerosol concentrations in *Adapted* are reduced to match in situ observations, most of the ice is lost to the liquid phase, revealing that the representation of ice in *Default* relies on high primary ice nucleation rates, which is not consistent with the observations of available INPs. When the efficiency and number of the SIP processes is increased in *Adapted + SIP*, the liquid occurrence is reduced again as compared to *Adapted* but mainly due to an increase of mixed-phase rather than pure ice.

Interestingly, Cloudnet and HoloBalloon seem to largely agree on the distribution of pocket lengths of any phase in the cloud interior shown in Figure 6d despite the large discrepancy in terms of overall phase partitioning. This close agreement in pocket lengths is interesting as it indicates that Cloudnet is capable of detecting the number and relative intermittency of phase transitions in the cloud despite not necessarily capturing the phase itself accurately. Both Cloudnet and HoloBalloon show a much higher frequency of the smaller sized pockets with the majority of pockets occurring on sub-kilometer scales indicative of a high degree of heterogeneity in the cloud. Spatial heterogeneity is captured in the model simulations as well with approximately 50% of the pockets being observed on scales of 5 km or less across the different simulations (dashed lines). When each phase is considered separately, we see that *Default* produces ice pockets that are typically much larger in size (Figure 6c). In *Adapted*, the relatively larger pockets occur primarily in the liquid phase due to a lack of ice formation in general. In *Adapted + SIP*, the enhancement of SIP increases both the relative occurrence and spatial extent of mixed-phase pockets similar to what was shown in Figure 5.

The mean pocket lengths shown in Figure 7a serve as a quantitative score for the interior cloud phase heterogeneity overall. HoloBalloon and Cloudnet both have a mean pocket length of approximately 2 km with the largest size contribution coming from the ice phase. *Default* exhibits less heterogeneity with phase changes occurring approximately every 10 km on average. With the observationally constrained low INPC and CDNC in *Adapted*, we see an even more homogeneous cloud with a mean pocket length of around 30 km due to the

dominant liquid phase and the missing ice production. *Adapted + SIP* ameliorates this heterogeneity gap by breaking up long liquid pockets and instead introducing more and longer mixed-phase pockets due to enhanced SIP. The step from *Default* to *Adapted + SIP*, both achieving satisfactory ice water contents compared to observations as shown by Schäfer et al. (2024), highlights the importance of the distinction between heterogeneity and mixing. Even though both simulations arrive at approximately the same degree of heterogeneity, with mean pocket sizes of around 10 km, their degrees of mixing differ significantly. *Adapted + SIP* exhibits pockets of true mixed-phase that are sustained over distances of approximately 7 km longer, on average, than those in *Default*.

5. Discussion

We find that ice and mixed-phase occurrence in the cloud interior is very low when aerosol concentrations are constrained to observations as in the *Adapted* simulation (see Figure 5). Additionally, RS, being the only SIP mechanism represented in the default Morrison scheme, was also found to be inactive due to the mixing ratio thresholds for its onset being too high for the clean conditions of this case study (Schäfer et al., 2024). This underscores the importance of including representations of efficient SIP processes particularly in these pristine environments.

Schäfer et al. (2024) point to the default Morrison scheme as being “right for the wrong reasons,” highlighting that the missing representation of SIP is partially compensated by unrealistically high primary ice nucleation rates caused by too high INP concentrations. When evaluated purely in terms of total cloud ice content, the default Morrison scheme is able to produce clouds that come in fairly close agreement with observations as shown by Schäfer et al. (2024). However, according to the results presented in this study, the source of the cloud ice significantly influences the cloud's microphysical structure. When ice mass originates primarily from SIP processes, as in the *Adapted + SIP* simulation, rather than primary ice nucleation, we see a much larger proportion of true mixed-phase (Figure 5). This is likely due to differences in where each ice formation pathway is most active within the cloud. The cloud top experiences the lowest temperatures (Figure B1) creating the most favorable conditions for primary ice production. By contrast, SIP is most active in the interior and near the cloud base as shown in Figure B2. In these regions, the total water content is also high (Figure 4) making a transition from liquid to mixed-phase likely when SIP is enhanced. The differing impacts of primary and secondary ice on the cloud's microphysical structure are important, as any increase in the mixed-phase proportion can act to destabilize the cloud through a more active WBF process. These results emphasize the importance of representing each ice production pathway accurately in addition to achieving satisfactory total ice amounts in model simulations of mixed-phase clouds.

The observed cloud phase pocket sizes in this study are on scales ranging from the minimum detection size of 600 m up to around 10 km (Figure 6d) with a mean pocket length of approximately 2 km (Figure 7a). Modeled pocket sizes at Ny-Ålesund are larger across all simulations with lengths of up to 100 km being simulated and a mean pocket length of approximately 10 km for both *Default* and *Adapted + SIP* simulations. The discrepancy between modeled and observed pocket sizes must be seen in light of the spatial resolution differences between the data sources. Although the cloud is sampled here as a point measurement in both the model and observations, each time step is representative of very different cloud volumes due to the different spatial resolutions. Although Cloudnet observes the cloud through a very narrow vertically pointing beam and HoloBalloon through a small sample volume of approximately 3.4 L per time step, the model outputs cloud properties that are effectively averaged across a much larger volume given by the 1 km horizontal resolution. This means that some of the small-scale variability might be lost due to spatial averaging possibly explaining the gap from simulated to observed mean pocket sizes seen here.

The observed mean pocket size of around 2 km that we find here is largely in line with expectations following previous research on the topic of cloud phase heterogeneity. Sokol and Storelvmo (2024) used satellite retrievals of cloud phase to compute an interface density metric defined as the number of transitions between liquid and ice per kilometer. For the latitude and season considered here, their findings translate to a mean pocket size of approximately 3 km for clouds of similar cloud top temperatures as observed in our case study. Similarly, Korolev and Milbrandt (2022) used airborne in situ measurements of midlatitude and Arctic clouds and found a mean liquid pocket size of around 2 km for the same temperature regime as this study, whereas ice and mixed-phase pockets were shorter at about 800 and 500 m on average, respectively. D'Alessandro et al. (2021) found a

similar heterogeneity signature with mixed-phase pockets being by far the smallest based on in situ cloud probe measurements of Southern Ocean low-level clouds. Their results also reiterate that mixed-phase clouds typically appear homogeneous only on scales ranging from around 100 m to 10 km, which is consistent with what we observe in our pocket size distributions (Figure 6).

The characterization of cloud phase heterogeneity through in situ observations, ground-based remote sensing, and cloud-resolving model simulations comes with important implications for large-scale models. Several past modeling studies have attempted to take cloud phase heterogeneity into account in ESM simulations and shown a significant model sensitivity of the global cloud radiative effect with regards to the treatment of subgrid scale phase distribution. Storelvmo et al. (2008) found that the glaciation process is significantly slowed down when subgrid scale variability of phase is accounted through a partially inhibited WBF process, consequently yielding a much smoother transition from liquid to ice phase in the simulated cloud. Building on these findings, Tan and Storelvmo (2016) showed that when lowering the WBF efficiency by limiting the contact volume between liquid and ice, the supercooled cloud fraction improved significantly compared to CALIOP observations, thereby indicating that the frequent underestimation of supercooled liquid clouds in ESMs could be attributed to unresolved subgrid phase separation in mixed-phase clouds. A similar experiment was performed by Zhang et al. (2019) where the WBF process was set to be active only in 15% of the cloudy grid cells as informed by airborne cloud probe observations and showed that this led to an improved representation of simulated cloud liquid due to a slowed down glaciation process. Results presented here indicate that cloud phase heterogeneity in ESMs should be represented over a wide range of scales rather than by a single metric for the in-cloud phase partitioning, and the phase pocket size distributions shown in Figure 6 provide a possible alternative. The methodology we present here also provides a framework for how cloud phase heterogeneity can be studied across a variety of data sources. This is crucial in order to evaluate the physical mechanisms influencing the heterogeneity structures and to ultimately form a basis for the development of a new physically based parameterization of cloud heterogeneity in future ESM simulations.

6. Conclusion and Outlook

Clouds observed during this case study were of a very heterogeneous nature, and homogeneous mixed-phase was not observed on scales larger than 10 km. Compared to the typical horizontal resolution of climate models of around 100 km, it is clear that the assumption of homogeneous mixed-phase clouds within each grid cell is inappropriate and likely leads to large biases in the representation of cloud phase, which in turn affects the cloud radiative effect.

WRF was able to capture cloud phase heterogeneity on similar scales allowing us to investigate the role of ice formation processes on cloud heterogeneity. We find that modeled heterogeneity is affected differently by primary ice nucleation and secondary ice production. Primary ice nucleation mainly determines how often the cloud is either liquid or ice phase, respectively, whereas secondary ice processes dictate how often true mixed-phase occurs in the simulated cloud. Our results indicate that cloud ice is “pathway aware,” highlighting the importance of accurately representing ice production pathways in addition to the total ice contents due to their differing impacts on the in-cloud distribution of phase.

We note that this paper is focused around a single case study, which may not be representative for Arctic clouds in general. Future representation of cloud phase heterogeneity in climate models is reliant on more comprehensive studies investigating heterogeneity over broader regions and over a longer time period. The case study presented here provides a framework for how such studies can be performed by combining cloud-resolving modeling with in situ measurements and remote sensing to provide a holistic view of cloud phase heterogeneity and its drivers essential to the development of physically based representations of subgrid scale heterogeneity in future climate models.

Appendix A: Heterogeneity at Cloud Top

The cloud top processes have in particular been pointed to as being important for several processes determining for example, the lifetime and radiative effect of persistent mixed-phase clouds. This is also the part of the modeled cloud most easily comparable with satellite observations, which provides further potential for future characterizations of mixed-phase cloud heterogeneity at larger scales. However, we note that for the cloud top, we do not

have in situ data from HoloBalloon as it did not reach these altitudes during any of the flights. Furthermore, cloud top observations from Cloudnet come with higher uncertainty due to strong ceilometer attenuation from its ground-based location. Therefore, we note that the basis for model evaluation of the cloud top microphysics is limited, which should be kept in mind for the following results. Still, we believe the results can provide interesting insights to be explored further in future studies.

In the model data, we define the cloud top as the apical grid cell at each time step with a cloud fraction >50% after excluding any occurrence of high clouds. Correspondingly, for Cloudnet, we select the uppermost grid cell classified as cloudy in the target classification product. Similar to the interior analysis, we look at the model column located at the Cloudnet measurement site in Ny-Ålesund and include a vertical range downward from the cloud top of approximately 200 m.

The phase occurrence at cloud top is shown in Figure A1. The cloud top appears almost fully glaciated in the Cloudnet target classification product. However, as previously stated, the uncertainty in Cloudnet increases with distance from cloud base due to signal attenuation (Illingworth et al., 2007), and so we note that there may still be liquid present at these altitudes that Cloudnet cannot detect. The *Default* simulation produces a cloud top of approximately equal parts liquid and ice but of a perfectly unmixed nature. At each point in time, the cloud top is dominated by either liquid or ice with little sign of an intermediate step in the mixed-phase regime in between. In the *Adapted* simulation, we observe a reduction in ice-phase occurrence, though surprisingly, not primarily in favor of the liquid phase. Instead, the mixed-phase occurrence is increased, and so liquid and ice are more frequently found in coexistence when INPs and CCNs are scarce. The connection of aerosols to the phase distribution at cloud top highlights the importance of using representative aerosols in numerical weather simulations. Between *Adapted* and *Adapted + SIP*, the occurrences of the different phases are virtually unchanged, indicating that the contribution seen from enhanced SIP is small at cloud top. This is expected as the temperatures at cloud top are well below the RS temperature range (−8 to −5°C). Figure B2 shows that BR is still active in this region, but the ice crystal production rates are not large enough to influence the mass balance between liquid and ice significantly.

The pocket size distributions at cloud top seen in Figures A2 differ from the interior (see Figure 6) in that the smaller pockets generally do not outnumber the larger pockets to the same extent. The Cloudnet distribution is impacted by the very low occurrence of mixed-phase and lack of liquid seen in Figure A1, and so most pockets occur as ice-phase of varying lengths disrupted only by a few isolated mixed-phase pockets. In terms of the model

Figure A1. Same as Figure 5, but for cloud top. Note that HoloBalloon could not reach cloud top and is therefore not included here.

Figure A2. Same as Figure 6, but for cloud top only. Note that there are no observations for HoloBalloon, and that Cloudnet did not observe any liquid at cloud top.

results, *Default* exhibits primarily a balance between liquid and ice phase as was also shown in Figure A1, and so the pocket structure shown in Figure A2 is determined by the intermittency of phase transitions between pure liquid and pure ice. These occur on a wide range of scales between 0.6 and 100 km with pocket lengths of around 10 km being the most common. When aerosol concentrations are reduced in *Adapted*, we see a pronounced shift in the distribution toward smaller pockets for both liquid and ice. When we enhance SIP in *Adapted + SIP* to replenish the ice, there is a slight shift toward even smaller pocket sizes.

The effect of SIP on the cloud top heterogeneity is evident from Figure A3a where the mean pocket length of *Adapted + SIP* is decreased compared to both *Default* and *Adapted*. Interestingly, this decrease in mean pocket length is seen across both liquid, mixed-phase, and ice pockets, meaning that when SIP is enhanced, the model produces smaller and more numerous pockets at cloud top (Figure A3b). Consequently, more heterogeneity is seen here with more active SIP despite the phase partitioning being largely unchanged.

Figure A3. Same as Figure 7, but for cloud top only. Note that there are no observations for HoloBalloon, and that Cloudnet did not observe any liquid at cloud top.

Appendix B: Supporting Figures

Temperature profiles of the model simulations as compared to the three radiosonde soundings is shown in Figure B1. The ice crystal number production rates through the various secondary ice processes in the *Adapted + SIP* simulation is shown in Figure B2.

Figure B1. Contours in panel (a) show the simulated temperature in the *Default* experiment, whereas panels (b, c) show the temperature difference between *Adapted* and *Default* and *Adapted + SIP* and *Default*, respectively. Color-filled black lines superimposed on panel (a) show the temperature as measured by the three radiosonde soundings released during the case study.

Figure B2. Ice crystal number production rates of droplet shattering (DS), rime splintering (RS) and breakup (BR) in the *Adapted + SIP* simulation.

Appendix C: Sensitivity to IWF Thresholds

Shown in Figure C1 are the cumulative distribution functions of pocket sizes in the cloud interior similar to Figure 6 but with varying phase distinction threshold IWF_T . The main result of lowering the IWF_T is an increased mixed-phase zone due to the more stringent single-phase requirement evident from the mixed-phase pocket size distribution being shifted to the right. However, when looking at the total cloud pocket sizes (panels D,H,L,P), that is, the pocket lengths of any consecutive phase, it is clear that the general cloud heterogeneity is not very sensitive to the choice of IWF_T as the pocket distribution shapes appear very similar both model simulations and HoloBalloon. The exception is the *Adapted* simulation (Figure C1h), which is shifted more toward larger pocket sizes at the lowest IWF_T of 1%. As discussed in Section 4, this simulation shows unrealistically low ice contents due to the much reduced INP concentrations and the cloud is virtually never classified as pure ice with the stricter threshold of 1% applied here, causing a stronger reduction in the shorter pockets occurrence compared to what is seen in the other simulations. Both *Default* and *Adapted + SIP* as well as HoloBalloon show very similar size distributions regardless of the choice of IWF_T , indicating that the phase distinctions here are robust increasing our confidence in the significance of the phase heterogeneity signatures.

Figure C1. Cumulative distribution functions of pocket sizes in the cloud interior per phase (columns) and data source (rows) with varying IWF thresholds IWF_T of 10% (solid) 5% (dashed) and 1% (dotted). Note that Cloudnet pocket sizes are not shown as the phase distinction is not based on our choices of IWF_T .

Appendix D: Sensitivity to Resolution Subsampling

The observational data and model simulations we use in this study come with different native temporal resolutions. The HoloBalloon product was post-processed to yield 30 s averages by Pasquier, Henneberger, Ramelli, Lauber, et al. (2022) matching the resolution of the Cloudnet target classification product. Although our model simulations also use a time step of 30 s, the output frequency is limited to 1 min. To ensure a fair comparison between the data sets, we applied a factor 2 subsampling to the observational data. The resulting differences in the

Figure D1. Cumulative distribution functions of pocket sizes in the cloud interior as observed by HoloBalloon and Cloudnet per phase (panels a–d) with original 30 s temporal resolution (solid) and subsampled to 1 min (dashed). Note that the minimum detection size for the pocket increases from 0.3 to 0.6 km when the temporal resolution is decreased.

pocket size distributions between the original 30 s and the subsampled 1 min HoloBalloon and Cloudnet data sets are shown in Figure D1. The minimum detection size of the pockets increases from 0.3 to 0.6 km as a result of the lowered temporal resolution in the subsampled data, which is apparent in the lower end of the distribution curves. Although there is evidence of a small shift toward larger pockets with the lowered resolution, subsampling does not seem to have a large impact on the general shape of the curves, lending confidence that our results do capture cloud heterogeneity signatures that are consistent across some variations in scale. However, this scale dependence of heterogeneity signatures should be investigated further in future studies across a wider range of scales to help bridge the gap from the micro- to macroscale view of mixed-phase clouds.

Data Availability Statement

The HoloBalloon data are available from Pasquier, Henneberger, Ramelli, Wieder, et al. (2022). The Cloudnet target classification data were generated by the Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure (ACTRIS) and are available from the ACTRIS Data Centre (Ebell et al., 2022). All python code used for the analysis and producing the figures are available on GitHub (Dammann, 2025). The modified Morrison scheme is available upon request from Georgakaki et al. (2024).

Acknowledgments

This study was supported by the European Research Council (ERC) through the ERC Consolidator Grant STate-dePendent Cloud feedbacks: enHANcing understanding and assessing Global Effects (STEP-CHANGE; ERC Grant 101045273) and EU-HORIZON-WIDERA-2021 Grant 101079385 (BRACE-MY). We acknowledge ACTRIS and the Finnish Meteorological Institute for providing the Cloudnet classification data set, which is available for download from Ebell et al. (2022). We would like to thank Julie Pasquier and everyone from ETH Zürich involved with the NASCENT campaign for providing the HoloBalloon data.

References

- Atlas, R. L., Bretherton, C. S., Khairoutdinov, M. F., & Blossey, P. N. (2022). Hallett-Mossop rime splintering dims cumulus clouds over the southern ocean: New insight from nudged global storm-resolving simulations. *AGU Advances*, 3(2). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021AV000454>
- Auer, A., Veal, D., & Marwitz, J. (1969). Observations of ice crystal and ice nuclei concentrations in stable cap clouds. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 26(6), 1342–1343. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469\(1969\)026<1342:ooicai>2.0.co;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469(1969)026<1342:ooicai>2.0.co;2)
- Bergeron, T. (1928). Über die dreidimensional verknüpfende Wetteranalyse. *Geophysical Publications*, 5(3).
- Bigg, E. K. (1953). The supercooling of water. *Proceedings of the Physical Society Section B*, 66(8), 688–694. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0370-1301/66/8/309>
- Bodas-Salcedo, A., Hill, P. G., Furtado, K., Williams, K. D., Field, P. R., Manners, J. C., et al. (2016). Large contribution of supercooled liquid clouds to the solar radiation budget of the southern ocean. *Journal of Climate*, 29(11), 4213–4228. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-15-0564.1>
- Burrows, S. M., McCluskey, C. S., Cornwell, G., Steinke, I., Zhang, K., Zhao, B., et al. (2022). Ice-nucleating particles that impact clouds and climate: Observational and modeling research needs. *Reviews of Geophysics*, 60(2). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021RG000745>
- Cesana, G., Waliser, D. E., Jiang, X., & Li, J.-L. F. (2015). Multimodel evaluation of cloud phase transition using satellite and reanalysis data. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 120(15), 7871–7892. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2014JD022932>
- Collins, W., Rasch, J., Boville, A., McCaa, J., Williamson, L., Kiehl, T., et al. (2004). *Description of the NCAR Community Atmosphere Model (CAM 3.0) (Technical Report)*. National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR).
- Cooper, W. A. (1986). Ice initiation in natural clouds. *Meteorological Monographs*, 21(43), 29–32. <https://doi.org/10.1175/0065-9401-21.43.29>
- Cotton, R. J., Field, P. R., Ulanowski, Z., Kaye, P. H., Hirst, E., Greenaway, R. S., et al. (2013). The effective density of small ice particles obtained from in situ aircraft observations of mid-latitude cirrus. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 139(676), 1923–1934. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.2058>
- D'Alessandro, J. J., McFarquhar, G. M., Wu, W., Stith, J. L., Jensen, J. B., & Rauber, R. M. (2021). Characterizing the occurrence and spatial heterogeneity of liquid, ice, and mixed phase low-level clouds over the southern ocean using in situ observations acquired during SOCRATES. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 126(11), e2020JD034482. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020JD034482>
- Dammann, S. (2025). Supporting code for Dammann et al. “observations and model simulations of phase heterogeneity in Arctic clouds”. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15100626>
- David, R. O., Cascajo-Castresana, M., Brennan, K. P., Rösch, M., Els, N., Werz, J., et al. (2019). Development of the DRoplet Ice Nuclei Counter Zurich (DRINCZ): Validation and application to field-collected snow samples. *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*, 12(12), 6865–6888. <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-12-6865-2019>

- Ebell, K., Maturilli, M., & O'Connor, E. (2022). *Classification data from Ny-Ålesund on 12 November 2019*. ACTRIS Cloud remote sensing data centre unit (CLU). Retrieved from <https://hdl.handle.net/21.12132/1.9170b333642f41ab>
- Field, P. R., Lawson, R. P., Brown, P. R. A., Lloyd, G., Westbrook, C., Moisseev, D., & Sullivan, S. (2017). Secondary ice production: Current state of the science and recommendations for the future. *Meteorological Monographs*, 58(1), 7.1–7.20. <https://doi.org/10.1175/AMSMONOGRAPHIS-D-16-0014.1>
- Findeisen, W. (1938). Kolloid-meteorologische Vorgänge bei Neiderschlags-bildung. *Meteorologische Zeitschrift*, 55, 121–133.
- Georgakaki, P., Sotiropoulou, G., & Nenes, A. (2024). Updated Morrison cloud microphysics scheme for WRF including ice multiplication processes. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13257171>
- Georgakaki, P., Sotiropoulou, G., Vignon, É., Billault-Roux, A.-C., Berne, A., & Nenes, A. (2022). Secondary ice production processes in wintertime alpine mixed-phase clouds. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 22(3), 1965–1988. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-22-1965-2022>
- Griesche, H. J., Seifert, P., Ansmann, A., Baars, H., Barrientos Velasco, C., Bühl, J., et al. (2020). Application of the shipborne remote sensing supersite OCEANET for profiling of Arctic aerosols and clouds during *Polarstern* cruise PS106. *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*, 13(10), 5335–5358. <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-13-5335-2020>
- Hallett, J., & Mossop, S. C. (1974). Production of secondary ice particles during the riming process. *Nature*, 249(5452), 26–28. <https://doi.org/10.1038/249026a0>
- Hersbach, H., Bell, B., Biavati, G., Horányi, A., Muñoz Sabater, J., Nicolas, J., et al. (2023). ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1940 to present. *Copernicus Climate Change Service(C3S)*. <https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.adbb2447>
- Hobbs, P. V., & Rangno, A. L. (1990). Rapid development of high ice particle concentrations in small polar maritime cumuliform clouds. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 47(22), 2710–2722. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469\(1990\)047<2710:rdohip>2.0.co;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469(1990)047<2710:rdohip>2.0.co;2)
- Hobbs, P. V., & Rangno, A. L. (1998). Microstructures of low and middle-level clouds over the Beaufort Sea. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 124(550), 2035–2071. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.49712455012>
- Hogan, R. J., & O'Connor, E. (2004). *Facilitating cloud radar and lidar algorithms: the Cloudnet Instrument Synergy/Target Categorization product (Tech. Rep.)*. University of Reading, UK: Dept. of Meteorology.
- Hong, S.-Y., Noh, Y., & Dudhia, J. (2006). A new vertical diffusion package with an explicit treatment of entrainment processes. *Monthly Weather Review*, 134(9), 2318–2341. <https://doi.org/10.1175/MWR3199.1>
- Illingworth, A. J., Hogan, R. J., O'Connor, E. J., Bouniol, D., Brooks, M. E., Delanoé, J., et al. (2007). Cloudnet. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 88(6), 883–898. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-88-6-883>
- Kanji, Z. A., Ladino, L. A., Wex, H., Boose, Y., Burkert-Kohn, M., Cziczko, D. J., & Krämer, M. (2017). Overview of ice nucleating particles. *Meteorological Monographs*, 58(1), 1.1–1.33. <https://doi.org/10.1175/AMSMONOGRAPHIS-D-16-0006.1>
- Koenig, L. R. (1963). The glaciating behavior of small cumulonimbus clouds. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 20(1), 29–47. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469\(1963\)020<0029:tgbose>2.0.co;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469(1963)020<0029:tgbose>2.0.co;2)
- Komurcu, M., Storelvmo, T., Tan, I., Lohmann, U., Yun, Y., Penner, J. E., et al. (2014). Intercomparison of the cloud water phase among global climate models. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 119(6), 3372–3400. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2013JD021119>
- Korolev, A., Isaac, G. A., Cober, S. G., Strapp, J. W., & Hallett, J. (2003). Microphysical characterization of mixed-phase clouds. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 129(587), 39–65. <https://doi.org/10.1256/qj.01.204>
- Korolev, A., & Leisner, T. (2020). Review of experimental studies of secondary ice production. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 20(20), 11767–11797. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-20-11767-2020>
- Korolev, A., McFarquhar, G., Field, P. R., Franklin, C., Lawson, P., Wang, Z., et al. (2017). Mixed-phase clouds: Progress and challenges. *Meteorological Monographs*, 58(1), 5.1–5.50. <https://doi.org/10.1175/AMSMONOGRAPHIS-D-17-0001.1>
- Korolev, A., & Milbrandt, J. (2022). How are mixed-phase clouds mixed? *Geophysical Research Letters*, 49(18). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GL099578>
- Ladino, L. A., Korolev, A., Heckman, I., Wolde, M., Fridlind, A. M., & Ackerman, A. S. (2017). On the role of ice-nucleating aerosol in the formation of ice particles in tropical mesoscale convective systems. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 44(3), 1574–1582. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016GL072455>
- Lauber, A., Kiselev, A., Pander, T., Handmann, P., & Leisner, T. (2018). Secondary ice formation during freezing of levitated droplets. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 75(8), 2815–2826. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JAS-D-18-0052.1>
- Maciel, F. V., Diao, M., & Yang, C. A. (2024). Partition between supercooled liquid droplets and ice crystals in mixed-phase clouds based on airborne in situ observations. *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*, 17(16), 4843–4861. <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-17-4843-2024>
- Matus, A. V., & L'Ecuyer, T. S. (2017). The role of cloud phase in Earth's radiation budget. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 122(5), 2559–2578. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016JD025951>
- McCoy, D. T., Hartmann, D. L., Zelinka, M. D., Ceppi, P., & Grosvenor, D. P. (2015). Mixed-phase cloud physics and Southern Ocean cloud feedback in climate models. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 120(18), 9539–9554. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015JD023603>
- McIlhattan, E. A., L'Ecuyer, T. S., & Miller, N. B. (2017). Observational evidence linking arctic supercooled liquid cloud biases in CESM to snowfall processes. *Journal of Climate*, 30(12), 4477–4495. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-16-0666.1>
- Meyers, M. P., DeMott, P. J., & Cotton, W. R. (1992). New primary ice-nucleation parameterizations in an explicit cloud model. *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology*, 31(7), 708–721. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0450\(1992\)031<0708:npinpi>2.0.co;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0450(1992)031<0708:npinpi>2.0.co;2)
- Morrison, H., Curry, J. A., & Khvorostyanov, V. I. (2005). A new double-moment microphysics parameterization for application in cloud and climate models. Part I: Description. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 62(6), 1665–1677. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JAS3446.1>
- Morrison, H., & Grabowski, W. W. (2008). A novel approach for representing ice microphysics in models: Description and tests using a kinematic framework. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 65(5), 1528–1548. <https://doi.org/10.1175/2007AS2491.1>
- Mülmenstädt, J., Sourdeval, O., Delanoé, J., & Quaas, J. (2015). Frequency of occurrence of rain from liquid-mixed-and ice-phase clouds derived from A-Train satellite retrievals. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 42(15), 6502–6509. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015GL064604>
- Naud, C. M., Booth, J. F., & Genio, A. D. D. (2014). Evaluation of ERA-interim and MERRA cloudiness in the southern ocean. *Journal of Climate*, 27(5), 2109–2124. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-13-00432.1>
- Pasquier, J. T., David, R. O., Freitas, G., Gierens, R., Gramlich, Y., Haslett, S., et al. (2022). The Ny-Ålesund Aerosol Cloud Experiment (NASCENT): Overview and first results. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 103(11), E2533–E2558. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-21-0034.1>
- Pasquier, J. T., Henneberger, J., Ramelli, F., Lauber, A., David, R. O., Wieder, J., et al. (2022). Conditions favorable for secondary ice production in Arctic mixed-phase clouds. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 22(23), 15579–15601. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-22-15579-2022>
- Pasquier, J. T., Henneberger, J., Ramelli, F., Wieder, J., Gierens, R., Ebell, K., et al. (2022). Data from the NASCENT campaign used in the publications: “conditions favorable for secondary ice production in Arctic mixed-phase clouds” and “understanding the history of two complex ice crystal habits deduced from a holographic imager. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7402285>

- Phillips, V. T. J., Patade, S., Gutierrez, J., & Bansemer, A. (2018). Secondary ice production by fragmentation of freezing drops: Formulation and theory. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 75(9), 3031–3070. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JAS-D-17-0190.1>
- Ramelli, F., Beck, A., Henneberger, J., & Lohmann, U. (2020). Using a holographic imager on a tethered balloon system for microphysical observations of boundary layer clouds. *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*, 13(2), 925–939. <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-13-925-2020>
- Schäfer, B., David, R. O., Georgakaki, P., Pasquier, J. T., Sotiropoulou, G., & Storelvmo, T. (2024). Simulations of primary and secondary ice production during an Arctic mixed-phase cloud case from the Ny-Ålesund Aerosol Cloud Experiment (NASCENT) campaign. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 24(12), 7179–7202. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-24-7179-2024>
- Shupe, M. D., Daniel, J. S., de Boer, G., Eloranta, E. W., Kollias, P., Long, C. N., et al. (2008). A focus on mixed-phase clouds. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 89(10), 1549–1562. <https://doi.org/10.1175/2008BAMS2378.1>
- Sinclair, V. A., Moiseev, D., & von Lerber, A. (2016). How dual-polarization radar observations can be used to verify model representation of secondary ice. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 121(18), 10954–10970. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016JD025381>
- Skamarock, W. C., Klemp, J. B., Dudhia, J., Gill, D. O., Barker, D. M., Wang, W., & Powers, J. G. (2019). *A description of the advanced research WRF version 4 (Technical report)*. National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR).
- Sokol, A. B., & Storelvmo, T. (2024). The spatial heterogeneity of cloud phase observed by satellite. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 129(3). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023JD039751>
- Sotiropoulou, G., Vignon, É., Young, G., Morrison, H., O'Shea, S., Lachlan-Cope, T., et al. (2021). Secondary ice production in summer clouds over the Antarctic coast: An underappreciated process in atmospheric models. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 21(2), 755–771. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-21-755-2021>
- Storelvmo, T., Kristjánsson, J. E., Lohmann, U., Iversen, T., Kirkevåg, A., & Seland, Ø. (2008). Modeling of the Wegener–Bergeron–Findeisen process—Implications for aerosol indirect effects. *Environmental Research Letters*, 3(4), 045001. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/3/4/045001>
- Tan, I., & Storelvmo, T. (2016). Sensitivity study on the influence of cloud microphysical parameters on mixed-phase cloud thermodynamic phase partitioning in CAM5. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 73(2), 709–728. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JAS-D-15-0152.1>
- Touloupas, G., Lauber, A., Henneberger, J., Beck, A., & Lucchi, A. (2020). A convolutional neural network for classifying cloud particles recorded by imaging probes. *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*, 13(5), 2219–2239. <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-13-2219-2020>
- Vali, G. (1971). Quantitative evaluation of experimental results on the heterogeneous freezing nucleation of supercooled liquids. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 28(3), 402–409. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469\(1971\)028<0402:QEOERA>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469(1971)028<0402:QEOERA>2.0.CO;2)
- Vardiman, L. (1978). The generation of secondary ice particles in clouds by crystal–crystal collision. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 35(11), 2168–2180. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469\(1978\)035<2168:TGOSIP>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469(1978)035<2168:TGOSIP>2.0.CO;2)
- Vergara-Temprado, J., Miltenberger, A. K., Furtado, K., Grosvenor, D. P., Shipway, B. J., Hill, A. A., et al. (2018). Strong control of Southern Ocean cloud reflectivity by ice-nucleating particles. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 115(11), 2687–2692. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1721627115>
- Wegener, A. (1911). In J. A. Barth (Ed.), *Thermodynamik der atmosphäre*.
- Wieder, J., Ihn, N., Mignani, C., Haarig, M., Bühl, J., Seifert, P., et al. (2022). Retrieving ice-nucleating particle concentration and ice multiplication factors using active remote sensing validated by in situ observations. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 22(15), 9767–9797. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-22-9767-2022>
- Wieder, J., Mignani, C., Schär, M., Roth, L., Sprenger, M., Henneberger, J., et al. (2022). Unveiling atmospheric transport and mixing mechanisms of ice-nucleating particles over the Alps. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 22(5), 3111–3130. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-22-3111-2022>
- Yang, J., Qin, Z., Deng, Y., Chen, M., Jing, X., Yin, Y., et al. (2024). On the cluster scales of hydrometeors in mixed-phase stratiform clouds. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 51(11). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024GL108166>
- Young, G., Lachlan-Cope, T., O'Shea, S. J., Dearden, C., Listowski, C., Bower, K. N., et al. (2019). Radiative effects of secondary ice enhancement in coastal Antarctic clouds. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 46(4), 2312–2321. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018GL080551>
- Zhang, M., Liu, X., Diao, M., D'Alessandro, J. J., Wang, Y., Wu, C., et al. (2019). Impacts of representing heterogeneous distribution of cloud liquid and ice on phase partitioning of Arctic mixed-phase clouds with NCAR CAM5. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 124(23), 13071–13090. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019JD030502>